

WHAT DO TEACHERS IN UPPER SECONDARY SCHOOLS THINK AND DO TO INTEGRATE CULTURE IN EFL TEACHING?

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ABSTRACT

Integrating culture into teaching a foreign language is not a new but controversial issue especially in general education. In the context of global and regional integration, it has gained a better positionality in teaching and learning English in Vietnam. In fact, intercultural objectives and intercultural content have been added as part of the expected curriculum and pilot coursebooks for teaching English in upper secondary education. Prior to the implementation of the new curriculum, it is essential to explore the status of intercultural integration: how teachers think and do. This study aims to investigate teachers' perceptions and practices of incorporating culture into English lessons to develop learners' intercultural communicative competence. Data collected from 105 teachers' responses to a questionnaire and open-ended questions proved that (1) teachers had good understandings of intercultural language teaching but (2) they rarely conducted intercultural activities in practice. The findings suggest that integrating culture into EFL classrooms in general education needs more attentions from teachers and educational administrators.

Key words: Intercultural competence, intercultural teaching, integrating culture, general education, teachers' perceptions and practices

1 INTRODUCTION

In response to regional and global integration, the incorporation of teaching cultures to teaching English to enable learners to communicate across linguistic and cultural boundaries successfully has become an increasing trend (Byram & Kramsch, 2008). In the same line, Vietnamese language-in-education policy has focused on developing intercultural competence (IC) for the students in general education as an innovation of reformation. According to Nguyen (cited in Quang Anh, 2018), the reformed curriculum for teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) is noticeable with the integration of cultural content. Hoang (2016) confirmed that intercultural content was added to develop learners' communicative competence (CC) and approach to comprehensive IC.

As an evidence of intercultural integration, since 2014, a new coursebook version (still at pilot stage, hereafter called by pilot coursebooks) has been applied simultaneously with and gradually in replace for the current version (also known as standard coursebooks). Evaluating intercultural content in grade 10 coursebook, volume 1, Lai (2016) proved that the proportion of home, target,

and international culture is 51%, 31%, and 18% respectively. Cultural diversity in the pilot curriculum is not limited to native English-speaking countries but extension to others, such as Singapore, Malaysia, China, Thailand, South Korea, and Japan (Hoang, 2018).

To strengthen teachers' implementation, this study aims to explore to what degree the teachers are acknowledged of and prepared for the intentional integration of culture into their teaching. Specifically, the research issues are expressed in two research questions.

1. How do EFL teachers in upper secondary schools perceive the objectives and practices of intercultural integration?
2. To what extent do teachers implement intercultural integration in their teaching?

From the view of intentional intercultural integration to develop students' CC and IC, intercultural teaching principles are specified.

2 LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical backgrounds

Culture and Intercultural Competence

Culture has been viewed differently: analytic or holistic, concrete or abstract, and static or dynamic. In the field of culturology and ethnography, Fraake (1977, pp. 6-7) believes that culture is "a set of principles for map-making and navigation". To Brooks (1997), culture is defined as the literature or civilization of a country. In language teaching, it should be viewed in relation to language because "culture shapes what we say, when we say it, and how we say it from the simplest language we use to the most complex" (Liddicoat, 2002, p.5). Additionally, culture is dynamic and ever-changing and so are practices, behaviours, beliefs, and values of cultural groups of people (Browett, 2003; Sewell, 2005).

Like culture, IC is defined accordingly with different constituents. IC, in this study, is defined as the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately within and across cultural and linguistic backgrounds in one's native language. Two noticeable models of IC in literature were introduced by Byram (1997) and Fantini (2006). Byram (1997) developed intercultural communicative competence (ICC) model constituted from five different components or five - *savoirs*: (1) *savoir être* - attitude, (2) *savoirs* - knowledge, (3) *savoir comprendre* - skills to interpret and relate, (4) *savoir apprendre/faire* - skills to discover and interact and (5) *savoir s'engager* - critical cultural awareness. Fantini (2006) proposes another model of IC, including multiple constituents and its four dimensions are knowledge, (positive) attitudes, skills, and awareness which are arranged in a spiral and dynamic circle. Intercultural knowledge refers to understanding of other cultures, intercultural skills referring to the capacity to engage in intercultural contexts, intercultural attitudes referring to the openness to the differences, and intercultural awareness referring to the feelings about the self in relation to the others. Since intercultural awareness is regarded as the most advanced level and built from active engagement in and critical reflections on genuine intercultural interaction (Ho, 2011), this dimension is not mentioned as part of IC in this study.

From the history of culture teaching, *culture as practice* is originated from dynamic view of culture (Newton, Yates, Shearn, & Nowitzki, 2010; Ho, 2011). This approach is widely receptive for aiming to develop skills to communicate and behave right in the target language culture, but it is blamed for ignoring the roles of learners' home culture (Crozet, Liddicoat & Lo Bianco, 1999). Therefore, Crozet et al. (1999) propose *intercultural language teaching* approach to promote students' acquisition of IC through intercultural language activities, namely exploring cultures and comparing home and target language culture. However, both the *culture as practice* and *the intercultural language teaching* approach ignore the interculturality of intercultural communication. Embracing the ideas practicing culture and acquiring culture of the two mentioned approaches, intercultural (language) teaching should aim to build learners' IC through their personal engagement in social intercultural communication in form of intercultural (language) activities (Byram, 2006; Deardorff, 2006; Liddicoat and Crozet, 1997; Newton et al. 2010; Newton, 2016). On that basis, Liddicoat and Crozet (1997), Newton et al. (2010), and Newton (2016) propose principles for intercultural integration or the integration of teaching culture in language teaching, also known as principles for intercultural communicative language teaching, which is briefly stated as intercultural teaching in this study.

- Intercultural teaching should expose to the learners as soon as possible.
- Intercultural teaching should be included in language lessons, not only a lesson by itself, but with a balance of cultural and linguistic focus.
- Intercultural teaching should be both implicit and explicit with clearly stated cultural outcomes.
- Intercultural teaching should foster learners' acquiring and learning process.
- Intercultural teaching should take the diversity of learners and contexts into account with variety of intercultural language activities.
- Intercultural teaching should aim to facilitate the learners how communicate effectively and appropriately in intercultural contexts.

In the light intercultural teaching, teachers' perceptions and practices in related studies are reported.

2.2 Previous study

A number of related studies in Europe (Gönen & Sağlam, 2012; Sercu, Bandura, Castro, Davcheva, Laskaridou & Lundgren, 2005; Sercu, María García, & Prieto, 2005) and in Vietnam (Chau & Truong, 2018; Ho, 2011; Nguyen, 2013; Tran & Dang, 2014) are found relevant to this study as they investigated teachers' perceptions and practices of intercultural integration in language teaching from the view of dynamic culture.

In Europe, Sercu et al. (2005a) aimed to figure out the picture of target language culture teaching in seven European countries. The most surprising finding is that language teachers in these countries dealt with culture in similar ways. First, there existed a gap between teachers' beliefs

and practices, and their relationship was vague. Second, culture teaching in Europe was more teacher-centred than student-centred. Activities were more focused on developing students' cultural knowledge and attitudes than skills. In another study exploring the perceptions and practices of Spanish teachers from constructivist view, Sercu et al. (2005b) expected the teachers to scaffold students to build their ICC by engaging them to multi-levels of input familiarity and meaning construction activities through social interaction. However, it was found that most cultural content was traced back to the coursebooks and high-ranking domains of culture, namely values and beliefs, were almost avoided. Intercultural knowledge transmission was dominant while activities to stimulate students' independent exploration and critical reflection were rare. Correspondingly, Gönen and Sağlam (2012) explored intercultural integration of Turkish EFL teachers and found that teachers had positive attitudes towards culture teaching and prioritized the activities developing intercultural attitudes and skills.

In Vietnam, Chau and Truong (2018), Ho (2011), Nguyen (2013), Tran and Dang (2014) confirmed that teachers' beliefs and practices of intercultural teaching were not consistent. Also, they concurrently agreed that teaching intercultural knowledge in their coursebooks was the most common activity. Chau and Truong (2018) and Ho (2011) further explained that teachers' intercultural integration was topic-dependent and accidental due to their considerable concerns of language objectives. Also, Chau and Truong (2018) and Nguyen (2013) assumed that teachers granted implicit and peripheral status to intercultural teaching. Tran and Dang (2014) proved that both VTEs and NETs were inclined to conduct activities to develop learners' intercultural knowledge, but the strategies utilized were relatively different. While VTEs incorporated culture in EFL skill lessons, utilizing artefacts, and inviting native English guest speakers, NETs told students about their own native cultures.

In sum, teachers were aware of the roles of intercultural integration and considered it as an integral part of language lessons. However, their practices were not in line with their beliefs and insufficient for developing students' IC and CC or ICC.

3 METHODOLOGY

Considering the methods applied in the previous studies and accessibility of data resources, this research mainly followed quantitative research approach with the use of a questionnaire and two open-ended questions (See Appendix 1). The open-ended questions were optional and in modification for data collected from the questionnaire.

3.1 The instruments

The questionnaire comprised two sections with 27 items focusing on teachers' perceptions and practices (Table 1). Its clusters and items were adopted from Chau and Truong (2008) and Sercu et al. (2005a). They were organized in a five-point Likert-scale questionnaire from *strongly disagree* to *strongly agree* for teachers' perceptions, and from *never* to *always* for the frequency of intercultural language activities conducted in class. Both sections of the final questionnaire achieved satisfying values of reliability ($\alpha_1 = .777$ and $\alpha_2 = .891$).

Table 1: Questionnaire description

Section	Focus	Clusters/ Factors	Items
1	Teachers' perceptions	teachers' beliefs of culture and intercultural integration objectives	A1, A2, A6, A8
		teachers' perceived practices of intercultural integration	A3, A7, A5, A9, A12, A11, A10
2	Teachers' practice	teaching intercultural knowledge	B1, B2, B3
		having students explore culture	B4, B6, B7
		developing positive intercultural attitudes	B12, B13, B14, B5, B15
		developing intercultural skills	B9, B16, B10, B8, B11

An open-ended question was inserted after each section to encourage teachers to share their own ideas or practices of intercultural integration.

3.2 Research participants

This research was conducted at the first semester of academic school year 2017-2018, when the two versions of English coursebooks, the standard and pilot one, have been implemented concurrently. One hundred and five (105) EFL teachers in the upper secondary schools in two provinces of Mekong Delta, Southern Vietnam, joined the research by giving their responses to questionnaires. Of them, 34 teachers have used both pilot and standard coursebooks and 71 of them using the standard version only.

4 FINDINGS

The quantitative results of teachers' intercultural teaching in terms of (1) teachers' beliefs of culture and intercultural integration objectives, (2) teachers' perceived practices; and teachers' practices, namely, (3) teaching intercultural knowledge, (4) having students explore culture, (5) fostering positive intercultural attitudes, and (6) developing students' intercultural skills are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean scores of teachers' perceptions and practices

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Mean ranking	Std. Deviation
Mean 1	105	2.50	5.00	4.2619	1	.49198
Mean 2	105	2.29	5.00	3.8021	2	.45298
Mean 3	404	3.00	4.67	3.6069	3	.45076
Mean 4	105	1.33	4.33	2.8377	4	.58644
Mean 5	105	1.40	4.00	2.8362	5	.62988
Mean 6	105	1.20	3.80	2.1295	6	.62016

As shown in Table 2, there is a downward trend from teachers' beliefs (Mean 1 = 4.2619) to teachers' perceived practices (Mean 2 = 3.8021) and teachers' practices of intercultural integration. Of teachers' practices, teaching intercultural knowledge (Mean 3 = 3.6069) is dominating; having students explore culture (Mean 4 = 2.8377) and developing positive intercultural attitudes (Mean 5 = 2.8362) were not often; and developing intercultural knowledge (M 6 = 2.1295) was quite rare.

4.2 Teachers' perceptions

Mean scores of teachers' beliefs are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Teachers' beliefs in intercultural integration

Items	Mean
<i>Average mean score</i>	<i>4.2619</i>
A1. Culture should be an integral part of English lessons.	4.53
A2. Integrating culture motivates students to study a foreign language better.	4.24
A6. Integrating culture fosters students' knowledge of foreign cultures.	4.23
A8. Integrating culture fosters students' communicative competence with people coming from other cultures.	4.14

Item A1, expressing the importance of including culture in teaching EFL, gets the greatest mean score (M A1 = 4.53). The high level of teachers' awareness confirms the position of intercultural integration in language teaching. In the same line, the other three items focusing on the objectives of intercultural teaching are high. Of them, the objective of teaching cultures for motivating students to study English was more approved (M A2 = 4.24) than developing students' intercultural knowledge (M A6 = 4.23) and building their ICC (M A8 = 4.14). As shown above, teachers agreed on the contribution of intercultural integration to students' language and culture learning.

Table 4: Teachers' perceived practices of intercultural integration

Items	Mean
<i>Average mean score</i>	<i>3.8021</i>
A3. Culture should be integrated into foreign language lessons as early as possible regardless of students' language proficiency.	4.00
A5. Culture can be integrated into language lessons in form of skill activities.	3.98
A7. Integrating culture can be done in form of intra and extra curriculum activities.	3.86
A9. Integrating culture can be organized by using internet applications (e.g. Twitter, Facebook, Zalo, etc.)	3.68

Items	Mean
A10. Integrating culture should include proper activities to take students' home culture into account.	3.65
A11. Integrating culture should include students' home culture.	3.91
A12. Integrating culture should involve clearly stated lesson objectives.	3.54

As presented in Table 4, that item A3 obtains the highest mean score (M A3 = 4.00) means teachers were acceptive of intercultural integration regardless of students' language levels. Next, the incorporation of culture to language skill activities was teachers' common idea (M A5 = 3.98). Regarding the role of home culture, teachers were more assured of its positionality (M A11 = 3.91) than teaching strategies (M A10 = 3.65). Also, using internet applications for interactive intercultural teaching was teachers' regular choice (M A9 = 3.68) but less often than those of face-to-face activities (M A7 = 3.86). Again, intercultural objectives got the lowest consent from the teachers (M A12 = 3.54). Obviously, the teachers had good understanding of intercultural integration in terms of intercultural teaching beliefs and strategies of implementation, but the recognition of IC objectives was not satisfactory.

Responses from seven teachers to the first open-ended question confirmed the dominance of intercultural knowledge transmission and the inferiority of intercultural teaching to language teaching. For example, they believed that teaching facts about culture such as the dos and the don'ts could help students avoid culture shocks in intercultural communication (teacher T45, T47 and T55). Also, other four teachers (T4, T16, T19, and T23) agreed that culture should be added to motivate language learning because it is close to students' interests.

From quantitative and qualitative reports, it can be concluded that teachers appreciated the integration of culture to facilitate language learning and developing students' intercultural knowledge.

4.3 Teachers' practices

Descriptive statistics of teachers' intercultural teaching practices is reported in Table 5. Mean scores of the four clusters display a downward trend from teaching intercultural knowledge (M1 = 3.60) to developing intercultural attitudes (M3 = 2.75) and skills (M4 = 1.87), from conducting teacher-centred activities to student-centred ones (M1 = 3.60 and M2 = 2.85).

Table 5: Mean scores of intercultural teaching activities

Items	Mean
<i>1. Teaching intercultural knowledge</i>	<i>3.6069</i>
B1. I relate the cultural contents to what I have learned and experienced about the foreign cultures or countries.	3.49
B2. I provide my students with appropriate language used in different communicative situations.	3.60
B3. I help my students to learn about how to do things and behave in different social interactions.	3.73
<i>2. Having students explore culture</i>	<i>2.8377</i>
B4. I ask my students to share aspects of their own culture in English.	3.27
B6. I ask my students to do kinds of projects to introduce their own or local culture to the foreigners.	2.58
B7. I ask my students to explore an aspect of the foreign culture and present it to their friends.	2.67
<i>3. Developing positive intercultural attitudes</i>	<i>2.8362</i>
B5. I mention the relativity of prejudices and risks of generalization.	3.08
B10. I decorate my classroom with pictures, ornaments, and so on to illustrate aspects of the foreign culture.	1.88
B11. I use videos, CD-ROMs or the Internet to illustrate aspects of the foreign culture like songs, films, fashions, festivals, and so on.	3.18
B12. I also teach the similarities between the home and foreign cultures.	3.36
B13. I encourage the students to explore the causes of differences the home and foreign cultures.	2.84
B14. I have my students approach to diverse cultural facts and notions to create positive perspectives towards the differences.	2.50
B15. I get my students to evaluate their home and foreign culture from different views.	2.40
<i>4. Having students practise language and culture in different settings</i>	<i>2.1295</i>
B8. I organize some simulated intercultural communicative activities like celebrating cultural events, role plays, solving cultural conflicts, and so on for students to practise linguistic and intercultural skills.	2.40
B9. I invite a person originating from the foreign countries to my class.	1.57
B16. I engage students into a chat group with foreigners to share their cultural knowledge and experience.	1.63

As proven in Table 5, teacher-fronted activities were the most common. Noteworthy, activities to deal with culture in communication and culture in language (M B3 = 3.73 and M B2 = 3.60 respectively) are more frequent than adding related cultural content to language lessons (M B1 = 3.49). Most of teachers' responses to the second open-ended question supported quantitative findings for focusing on teaching intercultural knowledge. In fact, 19 teachers reported that they added intercultural facts from their knowledge and experience to facilitate students' comprehension and attract students' interests. Noticeably, five teachers stated that they activate students' engagement such as cultural quizzes and guessing the pictures to encourage students to memorize cultural facts.

Among the activities to foster students' attitudes, three most frequent activities are comparing cultures (M B12 = 3.36), using audio-visual aids to bring culture diversity to the students (M B11 = 3.18), and mentioning relativity of prejudices (M B5 = 3.08). In support to the positive mean score of item B11 (M B11 = 3.18), two teachers reported that they showed students clips about cultural aspects of foreign culture such as fashion, music, and drama. Other advanced activities that required students' critical judgments rarely happened (M B13 = 2.84, M B15 = 2.40, and M B14 = 2.50 respectively). A simple activity, displaying artefacts, almost never took place (M B10 = 1.88).

Finally, the three last activities to engage students in real or simulated intercultural communication to develop intercultural skills were never or rarely conducted. Simulated intercultural activities quite rare (M B8 = 2.40) while activities engaging students into actual interactions by inviting guest speakers and joining chat groups were almost ignored (M B9 = 1.57, M B16 = 1.63). However, two teachers stated that they conducted role-play activity to have students solve intercultural conflicts to develop intercultural skills.

For most of the part, findings of this research echoing those of the others in the field are the inferiority of intercultural teaching and the domination of intercultural knowledge transmitting. However, this study has obtained its own values. First, what the participating teachers did by their own attempts to integrate culture was adding intercultural facts related to cultural themes in language skill lessons. Second, there was a gap between the IC objectives of EFL curriculum and its implementation from teacher reports. For clarification, while intercultural content and activities were introduced in the pilot coursebooks, no intercultural language objectives were stated, and not meaningful intercultural language activities conducted to develop students' IC at higher degree were found.

5 DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

In concurrence to findings of Chau and Truong (2018), Gönen and Sağlam (2012), and Sercu et al. (2005a), the participating teachers had good intercultural teaching awareness. In fact, they were ready for and acceptive to intercultural teaching. Even so, their ICC teaching objectives were not focused. Giving reasons for that, Hoang (2014) and Nguyen (2013) concurred that teachers lacked responsibility awareness to integrate culture into EFL teaching. Therefore, it was

suggested that teachers should be acknowledged of intercultural teaching objectivity as to develop students' ICC as an end itself, not only as a mean to develop CC.

Due to the insufficient positionality and objectivity of intercultural teaching, it was not properly treated in language teaching. In most of the studies, intercultural teaching was considered teacher-centred, knowledge-based, peripheral, and coursebook-dependent (Chau and Truong, 2018; Gönen and Sağlam, 2012; Ho, 2011; Nguyen, 2013; Sercu et al., 2005b; Tran and Dang, 2015). As observed in this research, what the teachers did to deal with intercultural integration was following the coursebooks and adding intercultural facts from teachers' knowledge and experiences to facilitate language teaching. The adaption or conduction of activities towards IC development was limited. Sercu et al. (2005b) assumed that teachers observed the language input and activities in coursebooks because it was easier and safer. Therefore, the availability of intercultural content in the pilot coursebooks allows the teachers to conduct suitable intercultural language activities to activate students' engagement for building IC and CC.

However, teachers could not improve this situation by themselves due to the overwhelming focus on teaching EFL for testing and overcrowded curriculum (Chau and Truong, 2018; Hoang, 2018). Besides, teachers' training on IC and intercultural teaching pedagogy have not been included in pre-and-in service teacher education (Nguyen, 2013). Without comprehensive pedagogical apprehension about intercultural teaching, teachers are at risk making intercultural integration dissociating and superficial (Sercu et al., 2005a). For those reasons, teachers should be supported and trained on the positionality and teaching pedagogy of intercultural integration.

6 LIMITATIONS AND CONCLUSION

This study has some limitations as follows. Qualitative data from the two optional open-ended questions was utilized to support quantitative data but not rich enough to provide an insightful exploration to teachers' perceptions and practices as interviews. The data were self-reported from participating teachers, not from other resources, such as the researcher's observation, so the results were not objective and comprehensive enough.

In conclusion, in the advent of educational reformation, EFL teaching is subjected to a change with obvious inclusion of IC objectives and intercultural content in the curriculum to enable students to communicate across cultural boundaries in English. However, intercultural integration has not been properly implemented in accordance with the stated objectives of the master curriculum. Therefore, to synchronize the implementation of intercultural integration from macro to micro levels, teachers should be encouraged and enabled to improve their intercultural teaching practices, which could be supported by more official guidance in lesson planning and implementing strategies.

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APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE AND OPEN-ENDED QUESTIONS

1. What do you think about the roles and practices of integrating culture into teaching language?

2. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neutral 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree

No	Items	1	2	3	4	5
A1	Culture should be an integral part of English lessons.					
A2	Integrating culture motivates students to study a foreign language better.					
A6	Integrating culture fosters students' knowledge of foreign cultures.					
A8	Integrating culture fosters students' communicative competence with people coming from other cultures.					
A3	Culture should be integrated into foreign language lessons as early as possible regardless of students' language proficiency.					
A5	Culture can be integrated into language lessons in form of skill activities.					
A7	Integrating culture can be done in form of intra and extra curriculum activities.					
A9	Integrating culture can be organized by using internet applications (e.g. Twitter, Facebook, Zalo, etc.)					
A10	Integrating culture should include proper activities to take students' home culture into account.					
A11	Integrating culture should include students' home culture.					
A12	Integrating culture should involve clearly stated lesson objectives.					

What are your own ideas about...

- the roles of intercultural integrations:

.....

- the practices of intercultural integration as you believe:

.....

2 How often do you conduct the below activities in your actual teaching practices?

1. Never 2. Rarely 3. Sometimes 4. Often 5. Usually

No	Activities	1	2	3	4	5
B1	I relate the cultural contents to what I have learned and experienced about the foreign cultures or countries.					
B2	I provide my students with appropriate language used in different communicative situations.					
B3	I help my students to learn about how to do things and behave in different social interactions.					
B4	I ask my students to share aspects of their own culture in English.					
B6	I ask my students to do kinds of projects to introduce their own or local culture to the foreigners.					
B7	I ask my students to explore an aspect of the foreign culture and present it to their friends.					
B8	I organize some simulated intercultural communicative activities like celebrating cultural events, role plays, solving cultural conflicts, and so on for students to practise linguistic and intercultural skills.					
B5	I mention the relativity of prejudices and risks of generalization.					
B10	I decorate my classroom with pictures, ornaments, and so on to illustrate aspects of the foreign culture.					
B11	I use videos, CD-ROMs or the Internet to illustrate aspects of the foreign culture like songs, films, fashions, festivals, and so on.					
B12	I also teach the similarities between the home and foreign cultures.					
B13	I encourage the students to explore the causes of differences the home and foreign cultures.					
B14	I have my students approach to diverse cultural facts and notions to create positive perspectives towards the differences.					
B15	I get my students to evaluate their home and foreign culture from different views.					

What are other activities do you conduct to integrate culture in your teaching?

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..... *Part of this questionnaire is referred from Sercu et al. (2005), adopted from Chau and Truong (2018)*